

VERTICAL SOLAR PANEL SYSTEMS: ARE THEY THAT GOOD?

Professor O.Z.Toirov., J.Sh.Abduganiev., S.M.Ablyametov

Tashkent State Technical University

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Annotation. This article ventures into the innovative world of vertical solar panels, delineating their departure from conventional horizontal solar panels and explaining the distinct benefits of this novel method of urban energy harvesting. When mounted vertically on surfaces such as the surfaces of buildings and poles, these solar panels enable the maximized utilization of available space and the ability to harvest solar irradiance from a wide range of angles all through the day. The annotation intends to conduct a further investigation into the multi-faceted advantages of vertical solar panels, including, but not limited to, their estimated energy generation potential, seamless integration with architectural designs, and potential to alleviate the current problems with relying on fossil fuels in urban development, during the worldwide expansion to renewable sources of energy.

Key words. Vertical, tracker, agriculture, agrivoltaic system, solar panels.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola vertikal quyosh panellarining innovatsion dunyosiga kirib, ularning an'anaviy gorizontal quyosh panellaridan ajralib chiqishini belgilaydi va shahar energiyasini yig'ishning ushbu yangi usulining o'ziga xos afzalliklarini tushuntiradi. Binolar va ustunlar kabi sirtlarga vertikal ravishda o'rnatilganda, bu quyosh panellari mavjud bo'sh joydan maksimal darajada foydalanish va kun davomida quyosh nurlarini keng burchaklardan yig'ish imkoniyatini beradi. Izoh vertikal quyosh panellarining ko'p qirrali afzalliklari, jumladan, lekin ular bilan cheklanmagan holda, ularning hisoblangan energiya ishlab chiqarish salohiyati, arxitektura dizaynlari bilan uzluksiz integratsiyalashuvi va qazib olinadigan yoqilg'iga tayanish bilan bog'liq mavjud muammolarni bartaraf etish potentsialini o'rganishni ko'zda tutadi. Shahar rivojlanishida, qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalariga butun dunyo bo'ylab kengayish davrida.

Kalit so'zlar. Vertikal, treker, qishloq xo'jaligi, agrovoltaik tizim, quyosh panellari.

Аннотация. В этой статье мы погружаемся в инновационный мир вертикальных солнечных панелей, описывая их отличие от обычных горизонтальных солнечных панелей и объясняя явные преимущества этого нового метода сбора энергии в городах. При вертикальной установке на таких поверхностях, как поверхности зданий и опор, эти солнечные панели позволяют максимально использовать доступное пространство и собирать солнечное излучение под разными углами в течение дня. Целью аннотации является проведение дальнейшего исследования многогранных преимуществ

вертикальных солнечных панелей, включая, помимо прочего, их предполагаемый потенциал выработки энергии, бесшовную интеграцию с архитектурными проектами и потенциал смягчения текущих проблем, связанных с использованием ископаемого топлива. в городском развитии, во время всемирной экспансии возобновляемых источников энергии.

Ключевые слова. Вертикаль, трекер, сельское хозяйство, агровольтаическая система, солнечные панели.

Introduction. Vertical solar panels, a departure from traditional horizontal configurations, offer a promising solution to maximize solar energy generation in urban environments. These panels, mounted vertically on surfaces like building facades and poles, capitalize on limited urban space while capturing sunlight from various angles throughout the day. One prevalent design is the vertical axis tracker, employing a rotating mechanism to optimize sunlight exposure dynamically. Fixed installations, on the other hand, maintain a stationary position, often facing south in the Northern Hemisphere for optimal sunlight capture. Crucially, panel orientation is key to efficiency, with perpendicular positioning maximizing energy capture during peak sunlight hours.

Innovative technologies such as solar tracking systems further enhance efficiency by adjusting panel orientation in real-time. This dynamic approach underscores the adaptability and efficiency of vertical solar panels, offering a promising avenue for sustainable energy generation in densely populated urban areas. Vertical solar panels exhibit versatility in their applications, offering a wide range of opportunities for sustainable energy generation in urban environments and infrastructure projects. In urban settings, these panels can be seamlessly integrated into building facades, transforming structures into renewable energy generators while minimizing land use. Architects and designers have embraced the aesthetic potential of vertical solar panels, incorporating them into modern urban architecture to create visually appealing and environmentally conscious spaces. Beyond buildings, vertical solar panels find applications in infrastructure projects such as noise barriers along highways and railways, where they serve a dual purpose of mitigating noise pollution and generating clean energy. Their adaptability to various vertical surfaces, including fences and streetlights, further expands their potential for integration into urban landscapes. As cities strive to reduce carbon emissions and enhance resilience to climate change, vertical solar panels emerge as a viable solution to meet energy needs sustainably while contributing to the creation of vibrant and eco-friendly urban environments.

Vertical solar systems, unlike traditional horizontal ones, are mounted vertically on surfaces like building facades, optimizing space utilization in urban areas. They capture sunlight from multiple angles throughout the day, potentially increasing energy generation efficiency, especially in shaded environments. Moreover, their seamless integration into structures

offers both energy generation and aesthetic benefits, allowing for versatile installations on various vertical surfaces. Understanding these differences is crucial for stakeholders considering solar energy solutions in urban environments. Thus:

- Less surface area exposed to dust, debris and droppings.
- Can be installed in limited spaces.
- More consistent power output during winter months.
- Modern and unique appearance.

Maintenance-wise, vertical solar panels are less prone to accumulating dust, debris, bird droppings, and are also less likely to be affected by sleet and snow in frosty regions. Their upright design facilitates easy shedding of most obstructions, minimizing potential interruptions to energy generation.

In tight spaces, opting for a vertical installation can save valuable room. Vertical solar panels can be installed in narrow spaces where traditional flat panels cannot, such as between buildings, making them a versatile choice for various settings.

Moreover, aesthetics play a crucial role. Vertical solar panels offer a blend of modern style and practicality, making them an attractive addition to any design scheme. They provide an opportunity to infuse contemporary flair into your home while showcasing a commitment to environmental stewardship.

Solar panel system type	Efficiency range
Traditional (Horizontal)	Typical solar panel efficiency ranges from 15% to 20%, and the most efficient solar panels commercially available are slightly above 22%. Some laboratory prototypes have reached efficiency values over 40%, but they are still very expensive and not viable for commercial use.

Vertical	10% - 15% depending on the circumstance
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According to The ecoexperts: “While they (Vertical solar panel systems) might not fully match the energy output of traditional rooftop systems, they offer the ability to use otherwise wasted space.”

Conclusion. Vertical solar panel systems hold significant promise for Uzbekistan, especially in agricultural settings. Their vertical orientation allows for efficient utilization of limited land space, making them ideal for farms and rural areas where land availability is a concern. Unlike traditional rooftop panels, vertical systems can be seamlessly integrated

into existing structures such as farm buildings and perimeter walls, minimizing the need for additional land allocation. This makes them particularly advantageous for agricultural operations looking to diversify their energy sources while maximizing land productivity. Moreover, vertical solar panels offer benefits beyond energy generation. In Uzbekistan's climate, where sunlight is abundant throughout the year, vertical panels can provide a reliable source of renewable energy to power irrigation systems, greenhouse operations, and other agricultural processes. By harnessing solar energy, farmers can reduce reliance on fossil fuels, lower operational costs, and contribute to environmental sustainability. Additionally, the vertical orientation of these panels offers advantages in terms of maintenance and performance. In regions with harsh winters, vertical panels are less prone to snow accumulation compared to traditional rooftop installations, ensuring uninterrupted energy generation during the colder months. This resilience to weather extremes enhances the reliability of vertical solar systems for agricultural applications, providing farmers with a dependable source of clean energy year-round.

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